

Comparison between data smoothing and preprocessing methods for double threshold

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Abstract— This work presents a computational investigation into several mathematical models, including moving averages, low-pass filters, exponential moving averages, differences of squares, and the difference between the input signal and noise variance. These models are employed as preprocessing techniques for electromyographic signals in the context of muscle activity detection through the double threshold method. The study compares both time processing and accuracy for each of these models. Additionally, the Wilcoxon hypothesis test is employed to ascertain the similarity among error distributions resulting from applying each preprocessing method in conjunction with the double threshold method.

Keywords — *Mathematical models, Preprocessing, Electromyographic signals, Double threshold, Wilcoxon*

I. Introduction

Surface Electromyography (sEMG) is a technique that consists of the caption of an electric signal provided by the muscle during a contraction [1]. From this biopotential, it is possible to obtain neuromuscular information, provide illness diagnosis, report the performance of high-performance athletes, and even control prosthetics members [2, 3]. However, it is necessary to preprocess this signal before using it. Mathematical operations constitute this preprocessing and require to be done in the most efficient way possible, keeping the morphology of the input sEMG signal [4]. In addition to data preprocessing, detecting muscle activity during exams and studies holds significant importance, as this time interval encapsulates the most pertinent information concerning the muscle. It is possible to use neural networks or mathematical models such as double thresholds where it is defined an offset and time interval delimit the start and end of muscle activity [5].

Usually, equipment designed for sEMG acquisition incorporates a microcontroller in its composition, which, in turn, presents process limitations. Thus, the necessity of higher precision while minimizing the computational processing cost is one of the central goals of this area. Based on this, this paper presents an analysis of different

mathematical models used for sEMG preprocessing, such as moving averages, low-pass filters, exponential moving averages, differences of squares, and the difference between the input signal and noise variance for the muscle activity detection with the double threshold method [6].

II. Materials and methods

This section presents the EMG data employed in this research, such as the mathematical equations for each of the preprocessing methods and the hypothesis tests to assess the obtained results.

A. Database

The sEMG dataset used was the Ninapro DB5, which was acquired from two Myo bracelets [8]. These devices are equipped with eight EMG channels and 8 bits of signal resolution and operate at a sample rate of 200 Hz. In addition to the sixteen columns containing the EMG signals, the dataset includes markers indicating the start and end of the muscle contraction performed by the volunteers. The data from the first participant out of ten was employed to validate the methods.

B. Double threshold for muscle activity detection

Analyzing the sEMG signal is necessary to determine when the muscle activity starts and ends. One of the most popular methods used for it is the double threshold. This method generates these two points (start and end) based on two limits. The first is a baseline used to detect a variation of the provided signal. The second parameter is founded on a window of time, which protects against false positives from noises. Then, the start of muscle activity can be ascertained when these techniques are aligned. In contrast, if one of these metrics fails to meet the predefined criteria, it indicates the conclusion of the muscle activity [7].

C. Smoothing methods

Before applying the double threshold method, it is necessary to establish a window of time [9]. The methods applied in this study are the moving average (MA), low-pass filter (LPF), exponential moving average (EMA), root mean square (RMS), root difference square (RDS), the difference between the RMS of sEMG signal and the standard deviation of the noise (NLR) created by the power grid - 60 Hz [10] [11].

In the moving average approach, the mean of the most m normalized recent readings is calculated and integrated at the vector x , Equation 1 - where i indicates the initial index and m the final index of the vector. Once the smooth signal is obtained, these values are passed into the double threshold process.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{n=i}^m x[n]}{m-i} \quad (1)$$

The low-pass filter usage attenuates a specific frequency band of the provided sEMG signal and frequencies below 65 Hz by applying a second-order Butterworth filter. Following removing these frequencies, a moving average, Equation 1 was subsequently applied to the resultant signal.

For the exponential moving average (EMA), it is essential to maintain a register of the last outcome derived from the expression. With this method, weights can be defined as the Equation 2 shows with the symbol α . Within the same equation, the value of i varies based on the amount of EMG data. After processing the m elements, with m being the size of the batch, it is possible to apply it at the double threshold, obviating the need for further application of the moving average.

$$EMA[i] = x[i] \cdot \alpha + EMA[i-1] \cdot (1 - \alpha) \quad (2)$$

The same concept is used from the previous methods for the root mean square (RMS) calculation. In a window of M elements, the RMS, Equation 3, is calculated and then saved in a vector that will be applied to the double threshold.

$$x_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m-i} \sum_{n=i}^m x[n]^2} \quad (3)$$

The Difference of Squares (Equation 5) consists of the subtraction of the variance of the noise from the RMS of the sEMG signal. However, creating a sinusoidal wave with the same frequency as the power grid is necessary, represented by the variable y . However, the sinusoidal wave must have the period and amplitude equivalent to the input data (EMG). After this, it is possible to determine the noise variance, as shown in Equation 4.

$$VAR = \frac{1}{m-i} \sum_{n=i}^m y[n]^2 \quad (4)$$

$$DTS = x_{RMS}^2 - VAR^2 \quad (5)$$

To determine the difference noise, initializing a vector containing a sinusoidal wave with amplitude and frequency consistent with the sEMG signal and grid power frequency (y), such as in the model Difference of Squares. From this vector, it calculates the standard deviation for a window of m points, Equation 6. Finally, it is defined as the difference between the sEMG RMS signal and the standard deviation of the noise (Equation 7).

$$s_y = \sqrt{\frac{1}{(m-i)} \sum_{n=i}^m (y[n] - \bar{y})^2} \quad (6)$$

$$NLR = x_{RMS} - s_y \quad (7)$$

D. Validation of methods

In order to validate the average processing time on each method, a standard window size of 50 was established for the double threshold. A window with sizes ranging from 30 to 190 was utilized for the sEMG data, with an increment of 10 points. The average time calculation was based on the outcomes from one thousand iterations of each respective method.

Two approaches were used to validate their accuracies. In the first approach, the window of time for the double threshold was maintained constant, while the number of points of sEMG used on the models was varied. In the second approach, these configurations were inverted by keeping the sEMG window constant and varying the double threshold window. At the end of each interaction, the number of rising and following edges detected by the double threshold was recorded, and this count was subsequently juxtaposed against the number of muscular contractions informed by the original dataset. This operation is represented by Equation 8, wherein D_c represents the number of rising edges detected with the double threshold, and C is the number of rising edges provided by the original data. The sEMG and time window for the double threshold adhere to the same pattern employed in calculating the average processing time for each method.

$$err = \frac{D_c - C}{C} \quad (8)$$

E. Hypothesis test

The statistical nonparametric method employed for validating the similarity between methods was the Wicoxon test [?]. The hypothesis model was chosen due to the volume of data utilized, facilitating a comprehensive comparison of the outcomes across each method.

The null hypothesis consists of a relation of equality between the outcome distribution of the compared methods; that is, there is no difference between the groups. Consequently, by rejecting the null hypothesis, it is claimed that there is a difference between them. Based on these affirmations, a statistical statement was formulated to denote the existence of similarity between the methods, such as sensors and windows.

III. Results and Discussion

A. Time domain processing

After the execution of the possible combinations between methods, time windows, and sEMG points, a matrix showcasing the average processing time of each method was obtained. Fig. 1, and Fig. 2 illustrate the average time of their dispersion for each mathematical method.

Fig. 1. Average time spent by each process to preprocess different numbers of sEMG points

Fig. 2. Histogram of the average time spent by each process to preprocess different numbers of sEMG points

B. Comparison between the errors of each model

Two matrices were generated to verify the accuracy of each model. The first matrix is the outcomes by changing the number of sEMG points, and the second matrix provides the precision by changing the time window for the double threshold.

Initially, a comparison of the error for each model was made, as illustrated in Fig. 3, and Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Error distribution for each method by altering the number of sEMG points

Fig. 4. Error distribution for each method by altering the time window for double threshold

In order to ascertain the presence of a correlation between a sensor and a specific mathematical model, a heat map was generated, Fig. 5, and Fig. 6, exhibiting the error associated with each model across different sensors.

Fig. 5. Heatmap for each sensor error by changing the number of EMG points

Fig. 6. Heatmap for each sensor error by changing the time window for double threshold

By having the error of each sensor across different methods, it is also possible to represent the error dispersion for each window used, regardless of the method and sensor. It is illustrated in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Fig. 7. Average error distribution for all methods while changing the number of sEMG points

Fig. 8. Average error distribution for all methods while changing the time window for double threshold

Table 1 and Table 2 contain the p-values corresponding to each comparison between the preprocessing models, considering variations in the number of EMG points and the double threshold window, respectively.

TABLE 1. P-values for the number of sEMG points

	Mean	LPF	EMA	RMS	RDS	NRL
Mean	1	0.691	0.002	0	0	0.957
LPF	0.691	1	0.074	0.045	0	0.037
EMA	0.002	0.074	1	0	0	0.12
RMS	0	0.045	0	1	0	0.018
RDS	0	0	0	0	1	0
NRL	0.957	0.037	0.12	0.018	0	1

TABLE 2. P-values for the time window employed in double threshold

	Mean	LPF	EMA	RMS	RDS	NRL
Mean	1	0.142	0.496	0.689	0	0.18
LPF	0.142	1	0.279	0.004	0	0.002
EMA	0.496	0.279	1	0.145	0	0.686
RMS	0.689	0.004	0.145	1	0	0.587
RDS	0	0	0	0	1	0
NRL	0.18	0.002	0.686	0.587	0	1

Applying the hypothesis test over the error dispersion based on the time window provided a matrix of dimensions 17x17. In order to facilitate the interpretation of the result, the heat map was used again, Fig. 9, and Fig. 10, between zero and one, where zero is the acceptance of the null hypothesis and one is the rejection of it for a significance level equal to 5%.

Fig. 9. Heatmap for results of Wilcoxon hypothesis tests while changing the number of sEMG points

Fig. 10. Heatmap for results of Wilcoxon hypothesis tests while changing the time window employed in double threshold

The p-values from the leading diagonal were not calculated since the Wilcoxon method does not allow the comparison of a sample with itself in the same conditions.

Analyzing the results of the average time spent by each method to process the EMG data, Fig. 1, and Fig. 2, it was noted that the first three methods, moving average, LPF, and EMA have a similar outcome and do not depend on the number of sEMG points processed. In contrast, the RMS, RDS, and NLR demonstrate a significant difference between them and have their time processing correlated to the number of sEMG points and time window used.

Upon examining Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, it is possible to verify that there exists a lower variance in error between the first and third quartile in tests involving variations in the number of sEMG points. Therefore, an initial preference for changing this number of points over modifying the time window employed in the double threshold.

Another notable observation is the relation between the error of each sensor on each preprocessing method. None of these methods demonstrated stability while analyzed individually; however, in conjunction with the double threshold, the RDS method exhibited a stronger inclination towards generating errors in detecting muscle contraction. Regardless, it does not discredit the method. After checking the outcomes from all methods for sensor S-14, it becomes evident that RDS exhibits the highest precision compared to the other methods. Also noteworthy is the similarity between the error for each sensor while changing the number of EMG points and the time window for double threshold. Sensors like S-0, S-1, S-7, S-11, and S-15 exhibited the highest average errors for all proposed methods. These outcomes could indicate or be generated due to the sensor position on the volunteer's arm or a fat concentration under the sensor area, which would cause EMG signals of lower amplitude [13].

IV. Conclusion

The preprocessing of the sEMG signal before its application in the double threshold method for muscle detection is essential. Among the six mathematical methods, it was determined that none of them displayed inefficiency, and there was no statistical evidence suggesting that one has method superiority in performance over the others. This leads to a preference for selecting preprocessing methods with lower processing times (like moving average, LPF, and MME) over the higher time-consuming alternatives (such as RMS, SRL, and RDS).

Through the Wilcoxon analysis, it was possible to confirm the similarity between the average error among the proposed methods. Again, highlight attention over the RDS method, which did not exhibit any similarity with other methods, regardless of the number of points or windows used. The focal point of the statistical analysis is around the relation of error distribution concerning the time window employed in the double threshold. One of these causes is that four distinct average error distributions exhibited similarity while altering the number of sEMG points. Additionally, it is worth noting that there is no time window capable of leading

to a rejection of the Wilcoxon hypothesis. Based on these findings, the selection of the time window employment in the double threshold and the choice of mathematical preprocessing method should be approached individually and adjusted to the specific requirements of each project.

Finally, for future studies, the number of volunteers from the Nina Pro dataset will be increased, such as using different datasets, to ensure that any preprocess method is not affected by the data used.

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